

ISic1108

I.Sicily inscription 1108

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

sandstone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

Theatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8807

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Σώπολις Φαλάκ[ρουτ]ὰν αὐτοῦτα ματέρα
2. [--]αν Φαλ[ακρ]ίαν εὐνοίας ἔνεκα

Apparatus

Text of Ampolo and Erdas 2019

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 653661

PHI 140591

PHI 175642

Bibliography

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